

Reliability assessment of thick high strength pipelines with corrosion defects

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Abstract This paper assesses the reliability of thick, high strength corroded pipelines subjected to internal pressure by first order reliability algorithms and Monte Carlo simulation methods. First, the predictions of different burst strength models, including a new prediction model for thick high strength pipelines are compared with experimental results. Model uncertainty factors are derived for intact and corroded pipelines to calibrate and introduce the uncertainties on the models used in the prediction of structural reliability. The uncertainty associated with model uncertainty factors is addressed and the best fitting distribution is identified. Extensive reliability and sensitivity analyses are carried out on intact and corroded pipes with calibrated burst strength models. Through sensitivity analyses performed for increasing levels of corrosion defects, the influence of basic parameters on the burst strength of corroded pipelines is characterized. The results demonstrate that the model uncertainty factors and the depth of corrosion are relatively important variables for corroded pipelines. The results obtained through reliability assessment are compared with that obtained by the strength model proposed in the RAMPIPE guidelines.

Keywords: Reliability; corroded pipeline; thick high strength pipeline; Model uncertainty factor; sensitivity analysis.

1. Introduction

Pipelines are the most important mode of transportation for the oil and gas industry. In order to improve efficiency, large and thick pipelines with high strength are used widely, as the larger diameter provides improved bearing capacity [1]. Considerable cost-effective design can also be achieved by using high strength pipelines such as X 80 and X 100. Moreover, the high strength pipelines may provide a solution to the deep sea or arctic area with geological hazards such as permafrost and semi-permafrost, landslide, seismic activities [2][3]. Still, failures occur frequently in pipelines with corrosion being the most prominent cause of failure mechanism to burst, collapse or other failure modes [4]. Like any conventional pipelines, corrosion must be the prime threat and given high priority in assessing the safety of high strength pipelines.

Corrosion is an inevitable phenomenon in pipelines whose investigation is of great importance to plan maintenance activities. Corrosion is a complex mechanism that reduces structural integrity and may lead to various failure modes in pipelines. Moreover, the extreme environmental and operating conditions may favor the growth of corrosion in high strength pipelines. Failure due to internal pressure is a common mode of failure for intact and corroded pipelines, the same may be considered as a foremost failure mode in high strength pipelines. The pipeline failure poses a potential danger to the personnel and environment; consequently, detailed safety and reliability studies are demanded. The first step in such studies is the selection of burst strength or pressure prediction models.

Extensive research on the analysis of burst pressure under internal pressure has been carried out for a long time [5][6]. For corroded pipelines, a comprehensive study has been conducted by Kiefner [7] who proposed an expression for burst strength of corroded pipelines. Later, Kiefner and Vieth [8] have updated this equation by modifying the criterion and showed its application. Based on such studies ASME introduced a standard known as B 31G to predict burst pressure of corroded pipelines [9]. One of the most widely used recommended practice issued by DNV deemed to provide better predictions [10]. The codes such as ASME and DNV have been validated using steel grades lower than X 70 with simple

defects, as a consequence of which these codes may not provide accurate results with high strength pipes in practice [11].

In 1999, US Minerals Management Services have collaborated with Petroleos Mexicanos (PEMEX) and Instituto Mexicano del Petroleo (IMP) and proposed an approach under risk assessment and management (RAM) for reassessment and requalification of marine pipelines known as RAM PIPE REQUAL project [12]. The RAM PIPE approach is based on stress concentration around the damaged area in the pipeline, this approach can be useful for any defect shape in high strength pipelines. These codes and approaches have been developed on detailed experimental and numerical analysis. Sometimes these codes overestimate the burst pressure based on high safety factors and impose unnecessary repair and replacement costs. On account for which researchers propose new methods and develop empirical equation comprise single, multiple and/or complex shaped defect.

It has been emphasized that the shape of a defect affects the burst pressure significantly [13]. Following this, many studies address the geometric model of corrosion defects [14][15][16][17]. In particular, Choi et al. [18] have developed an expression assuming rectangular and elliptical defect while Cunha and Netto have used axisymmetric flaws [14][15]. Chen et al. [19][20][21] performed a series of numerical analyses and recently proposed a burst pressure equation on the basis of geometrical (Double Circular Arc) model.

Reliability assessment of thin pipelines following design guidelines by ASME B31G [9] and DNV [10] has been the focus of study for a long time for many researchers. Examples of such probabilistic assessments can be referred to in literature such as [22][23][24][25]. However, reliability assessment of thick pipelines has not been conducted at the same extent, the recent advances in reliability assessment of thick pipelines can be tracked from [26][27][28]. The literature is scarce on thick high strength pipelines and not many models are available, This paper utilizes the new strength model which [21] has not been used earlier.

Therefore, acknowledging the above fact the research presented in this paper is intended to investigate the structural reliability of thick high strength pipelines. The present study utilizes experimental data to calibrate burst strength models used in the formulation of limit state function for reliability assessment of thick high strength pipelines. The First Order Reliability Method (FORM), First Order Second Moment (FOSM) and Monte Carlo simulation methods (crude and importance sampling) are applied to assess the reliability of intact and corroded pipelines. The influence of different levels of corrosion depth, operating pressure and other variables on reliability is demonstrated. This paper also investigates the importance of each basic variable on limit state function for both intact and corroded pipelines. This is an important aspect as it allows the assessment on how the variables of the new strength model of thick high strength pipelines influence the safety and how this influence compares with other traditional strength models. In addition, some parametric studies are conducted to assess the effect of thickness and yield to tensile strength ratio on reliability of pipelines. The results of reliability and sensitivity analyses obtained by Chen et al. [20] strength model are compared with the results obtained by RAM PIPE REQUAL approach.

2. An expression for burst pressure for high strength pipelines

Failure in thick pipelines differs from thin-walled pipelines in a number of ways, one difference being the combined effect of tensile and yield strength. Early research works by Faupel [29] have resulted in an expression containing yield to tensile strength ratio for the pressure pipes and pressure vessels. Faupel's equation was further modified by Brabin [30][31], using finite element analysis. Also, the failure in high strength pipelines follows elastic and large plastic deformation unlike brittle fracture in low and mid-strength pipelines [32]. Ma et al. [32] have also conducted extensive finite element analysis to obtain a new equation for burst failure of high-grade steel pipelines. Following up to these studies Chen et al. [21] have obtained a burst strength model for corroded pipelines. The proposed equation is based on a Double Circular Arc (DCA) – a geometrical model and the plastic flow theory – average shear stress for yielding is considered in this model.

Figure 1 shows the DCA model proposed by Chen et al. [20], which is made of two circular arcs. This method has certain advantages compared to its predecessor models [14][15][16][17] as it suggests no significant stress concentration.

The DCA model consists of two eccentric circles; the dashed arc represents the original surface of the pipe without corrosion. The center O is the same for dashed arc and the outer wall of the pipe. When corrosion occurs the center shifts to O' . Thus, the depth of corrosion (d) can be obtained as the length PM in Fig. 1. The depth of corrosion (d) to thickness (t) ratio can be expressed by $\left(\frac{d}{t}\right)$.

Fig. 1. DCA model proposed by Chen et al.[20].

Finally, a new burst pressure equation by Chen et al. [21] for high strength pipe with corrosion is given by

$$P_b = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \sigma_y \left[1 + \gamma \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_y}{\sigma_t} \right) \right] \frac{f_0 + f_1 \frac{d}{t} + f_2 \left(\frac{d}{t} \right)^2}{c_0 + c_1 \frac{d}{t} + c_2 \left(\frac{d}{t} \right)^2} \quad (1)$$

where, $\gamma = 0.65$ for steel pipes; σ_y = yield strength, σ_t = ultimate tensile strength, and:

$$f_0 = 2\lambda - 6\lambda^2 + 8\lambda^3 - 4\lambda^4$$

$$f_1 = -2\lambda + 8\lambda^2 - 12\lambda^3 + 8\lambda^4$$

$$f_2 = -2\lambda^2 + 4\lambda^3 - 4\lambda^4$$

$$c_0 = 1 - 4\lambda + 8\lambda^2 - 8\lambda^3 + 4\lambda^4$$

$$c_1 = -4\lambda^2 + 12\lambda^3 - 8\lambda^4$$

$$c_2 = -4\lambda^3 + 4\lambda^4$$

where λ is thickness to diameter ratio (t/D).

It is noteworthy that the proposed equation does not incorporate the effect of corrosion defect length, which could be a vital issue where biaxial stress states are considered. Hence, this equation has a certain domain of applicability as explained by Chen et al. [21]. This could be one limitation of this equation that can be sorted out in further research.

3. Assessment of burst strength model

The burst phenomenon under pressure in high strength steel is elastic-plastic in nature and it results in large deformation. Every strength model developed by experimental and numerical analysis so far has its limitation in applicability and so have a validity domain. Chen et al. [21] provided an initial validity check for their equation. Still, it is vital to verify this equation with existing codes. The codes developed by ASME [9] and DNV [10] are based on a large series of experimental and numerical analysis. So, the consistency of the present equation is checked with experimental results and codes like B31G, DNV and approaches like RAM PIPE REQUAL [12] for intact pipelines. Having obtained a sample experimental burst data for high strength intact pipe in Appendix A, its comparison with the prediction by Chen et al. [21], DNV [10], RAM PIPE [12] and ASME B 31G [9] is carried out. For the given models only physical variables are considered, the explicit design factors are not addressed in the study. First, these models are used for intact (corrosion free) pipe i.e zero corrosion defect. From DNV part B, the burst pressure equation for intact pipelines can be written as

$$P_{bi} = 1.05 \frac{2t\sigma_t}{(D-t)} \quad (2)$$

Whereas, B31G burst pressure equation for intact pipelines can be given as

$$P_{bi} = 1.1 \frac{2t\sigma_y}{D} \quad (3)$$

The pipeline requalification guideline project (RAM PIPEREQUAL [12]) introduced an approach to predict the burst strength of pipelines with corrosion, given as

$$P_{bi} = 2.2 \frac{(t-d)\sigma_t}{(D-t)} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 2. Comparison of prediction by a new equation with test data and prediction by codes for intact pipelines.

The predictions from DNV, B31G and RAM PIPE are shown in columns 8, 9 and 10 respectively in Appendix A. The results plotted in Fig. 2 show the proximity of burst pressure predicted by Chen et al. [21] to experimental data, DNV and RAM PIPE, although there are significant deviations of the B31G code. The high deviation with regard to B31G is due to the importance of yield strength in the code whereas the failure in high strength pipelines is governed by tensile strength. These results confirm the validity of the equation by Chen et al. [21] for the reliability analysis of thick high strength pipelines.

It is worthy to note that the validity for corroded pipelines could not be checked with existing codes like DNV, B31G since the equation by Chen et al. [21] does not incorporate the length of the

defect. However, it is possible to compare prediction from Chen et al. [21] with RAM PIPE [12] approach as illustrated in following sections.

4. Model uncertainty factors

The previous section explained the deviation in prediction from strength models from Chen et al., RAM PIPE, DNV, and B31G with experimental data for intact pipelines. It is irrefutable that no model can provide exact predictions due to the uncertainties involved in experiments or in models. The uncertainties associated with the experimental data can be reduced by carefully conducting the experiments, while the inherent uncertainties of the strength models can be reduced by engineering analysis. From the comparison between experimental data [20][33][34] and model prediction results (Appendix A), model uncertainty factors can be derived [35]. In the present context, the model uncertainty factors (M) can be defined as a mean of the ratio of experimental burst pressures to the predictions by burst strength models. Consequently, a value of M smaller than 1 represents an overestimation while greater than 1 represents underestimation of burst strength model. Further insight and the global definition of model uncertainty factors can be found in [25]. The M may be used to subdue the model uncertainties by comparing the differences found in the experiment and model predictions (see Fig. 2). The values of M for strength models for intact pipelines are presented in Tab. 1. It must be noted that the M represents uncertainties and its value may not be constant and must be treated as a variable. Thus, the first four statistical moments for M are presented in Tab. 1. Out of the notations presented in Tab. 1, Std Dev denotes standard deviation whereas, COV denotes coefficient of variation. Skewness is a measures of asymmetry of probability distribution of M about its mean. In general, kurtosis indicates the shape and tailedness of a probability distribution generated from sample. As the distribution for M is unknown and could be vital to observe in comparison with normal distribution, excess kurtosis is calculated here.

Experiment data is gathered [36][37] and presented in columns 1 to 7 of Appendix B. The predictions from models may deviate significantly from the actual burst failure pressure in corroded pipelines. Chen et al. model and RAM PIPE are assessed resorting to a database of 57 tests in Appendix B

and the predictions from burst pressure models are calculated in columns 8 and 9 respectively. From Appendix B, M calculated for Chen et al. model and RAM PIPE model for corroded pipelines is also shown in Tab. 1. It is evident from Tab. 1, that DNV model can be treated as most accurate for intact pipelines with the value of M close to one and the least COV. For corroded pipelines, it is interesting to note that Chen et al model overestimates the actual burst strength, whereas RAM PIPE underestimates the same. However Chen et al. model shows better correlation with experimental data and with less scatter.

The probability distribution is a vital property of a random variable. The skewness values in Tab. 1 indicate that the M may have a non-normal distribution. To identify the type of distribution for M , five well-known distribution types (Normal, Lognormal, Weibull, Gumbel and Frechet) are fitted to the dataset. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is conducted on the fitting distribution and it is found that Frechet is the most appropriate distribution among all types of distribution of M for all the models of intact and corroded pipelines. A schematic view of the Frechet probability distribution fitting over the data is also shown in Fig. 3, whereas the results (Kolmogorov-Smirnov test static - D_{stat}) of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests are shown in Tab. 2. Kolmogorov-Smirnov test static (D_{stat}) is defined as maximum absolute difference between theoretical and empirical distribution function of observed test data. For the sake of reliability assessment, the parameters of the Frechet distribution (scale and shape) are shown in Tab. 3.

Table 1. First four moments of Model uncertainty factors (M)

Moments	Intact pipeline			Corroded pipeline	
	Chen et al.	RAM	DNV	Chen et al.	RAM
<i>Mean</i>	0.968	0.948	0.991	0.981	1.235
<i>Std Dev</i>	0.0704	0.0653	0.0679	0.0882	0.1335
<i>COV (%)</i>	7.27	6.89	6.85	8.99	10.81
<i>Skewness</i>	0.5158	0.2044	0.2762	1.4765	0.8218
<i>Excess kurtosis</i>	-0.5277	0.8309	0.9731	5.1718	1.6150

Table 2. Kolmogorov-Smirnov test results (D_{stat} values) for Model uncertainty factors (M)

Distribution	Intact pipeline			Corroded pipeline	
	Chen et al.	RAM	DNV	Chen et al.	RAM
<i>Frechet</i>	0.148	0.111	0.127	0.295	0.122

<i>Lognormal</i>	0.200	0.145	0.179	0.350	0.183
<i>Normal</i>	0.212	0.156	0.190	0.358	0.204
<i>Weibull</i>	0.253	0.198	0.231	0.406	0.244
<i>Gumbel</i>	0.264	0.210	0.244	0.412	0.266

Table 3. Frechet distribution parameters for Model uncertainty factors (M)

Frechet parameter	Intact pipeline			Corroded pipeline	
	Chen et al.	RAM	DNV	Chen et al.	RAM
Scale	0.935	0.918	0.960	0.941	1.172
Shape	18.512	19.545	19.545	14.902	12.413

Fig. 3. Fitting of the Frechet distribution for model uncertainty factor (M) of RAM PIPE (corroded).

5. Reliability analysis of pipelines

The estimation of reliability of pipelines in the oil and gas industry demands high fidelity in the assessment method. This section is dedicated to the application of above-mentioned strength models in reliability assessment. The reliability assessment begins with the formulation of failure function or limit state equation. The limit state equation is defined here using the operating pressure (load) and the calibrated burst capacity or pressure (resistance) for the pipelines as given by

$$g(\mathbf{X}) = M.P_b - P_o \quad (5)$$

where M is model uncertainty factor, P_b is burst pressure and P_o is internal operating pressure. The burst pressure may be defined by different mathematical models available in the literature.

Based on the generalized form of limit state (Eq. 5), the probability of failure can be calculated as

$$P_f = \int_{g(\mathbf{X})} f_{\mathbf{x}}(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{X} stands for a vector of basic random variables ($P_o, \sigma_t, \sigma_y, t, D, d$) and generalized limit state function is expressed by $g(\mathbf{X})$, $f_{\mathbf{x}}(\mathbf{x})$ is the function of the joint probability density of vector \mathbf{X} . Failure is supposed to occur when $g(\mathbf{X})$ is less than or equal to zero. The region may be called a failure region, whereas $g(\mathbf{X}) > 0$ represents a safe region. The basic random variable vector \mathbf{X} stands for a physical variable with uncertainty in mathematical modeling, loading, dimensions, and properties of pipelines. To solve the equation, multidimensional integration of Eq.6 is required. A reliability index can be evaluated from the probability of failure as

$$\beta = -\Phi^{-1}(P_f) \quad (7)$$

where Φ^{-1} is the inverse of normal distribution function with zero mean and unit standard deviation.

The direct calculation of the Eq. 6 integral is rather complicated and requires vital computational effort. There exist many approximation methods to solve such problems which simplify the limit state equation. These methods can be categorized into two groups namely analytical and simulation methods. First Order Reliability Method (FORM) is such an analytical method that linearizes limit state function to find the most probable failure point or design points [38]. Another widely used analytical method is First Order Second Moment (FOSM) which utilizes first order approximation of Taylor series constituted from the limit state as shown below

$$g(\mathbf{X}) = g(\mu_{\mathbf{X}}) + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\partial g}{\partial X_i} (\mathbf{X}_i - \mu_{X_i}) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial X_i \partial X_j} (\mathbf{X}_i - \mu_{X_i})(\mathbf{X}_j - \mu_{X_j}) + \dots \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{X} are random variables and μ_{X_i} is the mean of \mathbf{X}_i . FOSM method assumes all variables to be normally distributed and uses the first two statistical moments that are the mean and standard deviation to solve Eq. 8. The approximate solution can be given as

$$\mu_{g(\mathbf{X})} \approx g(\mu_{X_1}, \mu_{X_2}, \mu_{X_3}, \dots, \mu_{X_n}) \text{ and}$$

$$Var \approx \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{\partial g}{\partial X_i} \frac{\partial g}{\partial X_j} \text{var}(\mathbf{X}_i, \mathbf{X}_j \dots \mathbf{X}_n) \quad (9)$$

The probability of failure in Eq. 6 can also be solved by a simulation method like the Monte Carlo method. Crude Monte Carlo (CRC) generates independent random samples of $\mathbf{X} = (P_o, \sigma_t, \sigma_y, t, D, d)$ from the joint probability function of basic variables. Another improved simulation technique - Monte Carlo Importance Sampling (MCIS) generates independent random samples of \mathbf{X} around the FORM design points.

The present study also aims to understand the effect of using different reliability methods or algorithms on reliability. The reliability indices are calculated by four reliability algorithms – FORM, MCIS, CMC and FOSM. The first two algorithms FORM and MCIS (with 10000 simulations) have been solved using COMREL [39] software package.

5.1 Reliability analysis of intact pipelines

The generalized form of limit state function given by Eq.5 is used for carrying out reliability analysis. The expression in Eq. (1) gives burst pressure for corroded pipelines. In case of no corrosion d becomes 0, resulting in $d/t = 0$ and correspondingly Eq. (1) reduces to

$$P_{bi} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \sigma_y \left[1 + \gamma \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_y}{\sigma_t} \right) \right] \frac{f_0}{c_0} \quad (10)$$

Based on test data (in Appendix A) the basic variables (geometric and material parameters) are assigned with mean values as the values used in experiment number 22 (see Tab. 4). The characteristic value of

operating pressure (P_o) is assumed to be 72% of the burst pressure of an intact pipe as specified in basic design criterion. Unlike low and medium steel pipe the role of flow stress no longer remains relevant in high strength steel and tensile strength should be used in the basic design equation (such as DNV [10]) which can be estimated from Eq. 2. The calculation for operating pressure is conducted using characteristic values of basic variables rather than mean values of geometric parameters and tensile strength (see Tab. 4 column 6). The mean and std. dev. of the operating pressure (P_o) are then calculated from the characteristic value and the measures of uncertainties adopted from [24] so that the probability of exceeding the characteristic value of operating pressure is 5%.

Table 4. Stochastic models for basic variables for intact pipes

Basic variables	Distribution	Mean	Std. dev.	COV (%)	Characteristic Values X^c ($x \leq X^c$)
Yield strength (σ_y)	Lognormal (parameters)	908 MPa ($\mu = 6.808$)	72.64 MPa ($\sigma = 0.0798$)	8	793.7 (5 % percentile)
Tensile strength (σ_t)	Lognormal (parameters)	992.8 MPa ($\mu = 6.897$)	79.42 MPa ($\sigma = 0.0798$)	8	867.8 (5 % percentile)
Diameter (D)	Normal	198.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.1	198.2 (50 % percentile)
Thickness (t)	Normal	14.6 mm	0.15 mm	1	14.6 (50 % percentile)
Operating Pressure (P_o)	Gumbel (parameters)	92.29 MPa ($\mu_o = 89.38$)	6.46 MPa ($\sigma_o = 5.039$)	7	104.35 (95 % percentile)

The basic variables possess inherent randomness and consequent unpredictability, so to cope with such uncertainties earlier reliability assessment may be suitable. Pattern and level of variability known as distribution and coefficient of variation (COV) respectively for basic variables in this study are assumed similar to that in previous reliability assessment of corroded pipelines [24]. The uncertainty that lies in dimensional parameters (D and t) are mainly due to measurement errors while the uncertainty in material properties (σ_y, σ_t) are due to the manufacturing process. The specific distribution parameters are also calculated where the distribution is not Normal. In the cases where the basic variables are defined as

lognormal distributions, the parameters are computed. In the same way parameters for Gumbel distribution are computed in the analysis.

The limit state function (Eq. 5) can be defined in three ways by using three different burst pressure models that is Eq. 2 (DNV), 4 (RAM PIPE) and 11 (Chen et al.). Also, the corresponding value of M with regard to each model is used. The estimation of reliability indices has been carried out using four reliability algorithms described in section 5. Table 5 presents the failure probabilities which are represented by the reliability index (β) calculated from FORM, MCIS, FOSM and CMC algorithms using Chen et al. [21] DNV RP F101 [10] and RAM PIPE [12] equation. It is interesting to note that the estimates from RAM PIPE approach and DNV resulted in almost the same reliability index. The reason for such congruence lies in the similarity of equations (2), (4) of these two methods for intact pipes. However, there might be significant difference between these equations for corroded pipes.

The estimates using limit state function with Chen et al. [21] results in higher values of reliability index than that of DNV [10] or RAMPIPE [12]. The influence of reliability algorithms can also be assessed from Tab. 5. In general, the FOSM and CMC methods overestimate reliability index than that of FORM and MCIS. On the contrary, the present study shows the different response of reliability method with different models (see Tab. 5). The limit state function with DNV [10] or RAMPIPE [12] model results in little higher values of reliability index with FORM and MCIS while Chen et al. [21] model predicts higher value with FOSM, than FORM, MCIS and CMC in the decreasing order. In general, the limit state function with Chen et al. [21] model results in a reliability index of 4.5 slightly higher than DNV [10] or RAMPIPE [12] model. The analysis estimates adequate value for reliability index for the intact high strength pipe.

Table 5 Reliability index of intact pipes

Reliability algorithm	Burst pressure model		
	Chen et al. [21]	RAM PIPE [12]	DNV RP F101[10]
FORM	4.51	4.14	4.13
MCIS	4.49	4.16	4.15

FOSM	4.55	3.88	3.88
CMC	4.39	3.85	3.86

Next, the sensitivity analysis is conducted to understand the importance of each variable on the uncertainty of the limit state function $g(\mathbf{X})$. This importance can be characterized by sensitivity factors (α) given by

$$\alpha_i = - \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (\partial g(\mathbf{x}) / \partial x_i)^2}} \frac{\partial g(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_i} \quad (11)$$

Figure 3 (a) and Figure 3 (b) show the influence of each variable on limit state function of Chen et al. [21] and DNV [10]/ RAM PIPE [12] model respectively for intact pipes. It is interesting to note that sensitivity factors obtained by using limit state function with DNV [10] and RAM PIPE [12] are exactly equal (Fig. 3b). A positive value of sensitivity factor for a variable indicates the increase in a variable will positively affect the limit state function resulting in higher reliability. The previous study [24] suggests that material strength is the most important variables in the reliability prediction of intact pipes, however, with the introduction of M it can be inferred that variable M is equally important in the reliability assessment. Operating pressure is the next important variable in both models. DNV code and RAM PIPE approach only account tensile strength while the Chen et al. [21] have included both yield and tensile strength in their equation, which are both important variables. According to sensitivity analysis on the model by Chen et al. [21], diameter and thickness have almost no effect whereas the thickness in DNV and RAM models have very little significance.

Fig. 3. α – values (sensitivity factors) for Chen et al. [21] (a) and DNV RP F101 [10]/RAM PIPE [12](b) models

5.2 Reliability analysis of corroded pipelines

Experimental data have been gathered on corroded pipelines with different levels of corrosion depth [35][37]. The specifications regarding material and geometry of pipelines used in one of the experiments [33] are tabulated in Tab. 6. The above section has already defined the stochastic modeling of basic variables for reliability analysis of intact pipelines. The type of distribution and coefficient of variations (COV) for geometric and material variables of corroded pipelines are assumed to be the same as that adopted for intact pipes in Tab. 4. Again the basic design criteria assuming an operating pressure of 72% of the burst pressure using characteristic values of basic variables of a corroded pipeline is used to calculate operating pressure in the pipeline. The distribution for operating pressure is also assumed Gumbel as done for intact pipelines.

Table 6 Stochastic models for basic variables for corroded pipes

Basic variable	Distribution	Mean	Std.dev.	COV (%)	Characteristic Values X^c ($x \leq X^c$)
Yield strength (σ_y)	Lognormal	840 Mpa ($\mu = 6.730$)	67.20 Mpa ($\sigma = 0.0798$)	8	780.1 (5 % percentile)
Tensile strength (σ_t)	Lognormal	980 Mpa ($\mu = 6.884$)	78.40 Mpa ($\sigma = 0.0798$)	8	853 (5 % percentile)

Diameter (D)	Normal	342 mm	0.34 mm	0.1	198.2 (50 % percentile)
Thickness (t)	Normal	13.54 mm	0.14 mm	1	14.6 (50 % percentile)
Operating Pressure (P_o)	Gumbel	47.22 Mpa ($\mu_o = 45.73$)	3.31Mpa ($\sigma_o = 2.578$)	7	102.6 (95 % percentile)
Depth of corrosion (d)	Weibull	0.25 to 5.75 mm ($\mu_o = 0.27$ to 6.21)	0.05 to 1.15 mm ($\sigma_o = 5.797$)	20	

The reliability analysis of corroded pipelines further requires stochastic modeling of corrosion defect in terms of corrosion depth (d). Teixeira et al. [25] have recommended that the variable depth of corrosion d may have 18 % COV; the present study assumes little higher value of COV that is 20 % as the high strength pipelines installed in deeper water may be associated with more uncertainties in inspection instrument. The d is assumed to be Weibull distributed and the parameters of Weibull distribution are identified from regression analysis (Tab. 6). Table 6 also summarizes range of corrosion depth and corresponding probabilistic parameters; a pipeline may develop high levels of corrosion with time.

Figure 4 shows the probability density function (pdf) of the corrosion depth for increasing levels of corrosion. It can be observed how the probability density function disperses about a horizontal axis with the average level of corrosion (\bar{d}). This dispersion indicates the increase in uncertainty associated with the values of corrosion depth.

Fig. 4. *pdf* of *d* for some levels of corrosion

For comparison purposes, the burst pressure equation by Chen et al. [21] is compared with that of RAM PIPE [12] in the limit state function since both models incorporate the effect of corrosion defects by only one parameter that is depth of corrosion. Also, predictions by Chen et al. and RAM PIPE approach have shown proximity for burst pressure (see Fig. 2). The RAM PIPE REQUAL [12] – the pipeline requalification guideline project proposed a burst strength model for corroded pipeline given as

$$P_b = 2.2 \frac{(t-d)\sigma_t}{(D-t)(1+2\sqrt{\frac{2d}{D}})} \quad (12)$$

Eq.1 and Eq. 12 are used in Eq. 5 to formulate the limit state function together with corresponding value of *M* from Table 1. To understand the performance of models, the reliability analysis is performed for increasing corrosion depths (characterized by corrosion ratio - *d/t*) and operating pressures.

Figure 5 (a) and Figure 5 (b) show the β - values (reliability index) estimated using the limit state function for corroded pipelines proposed by Chen et al. [21] and RAM PIPE [12], respectively for different corrosion levels. The applicability of different reliability methods is also addressed. It is interesting to see that the FORM and MCIS produce approximately the same results, as the same pattern

is observed in the case of CMC and FOSM. It is a known fact that FORM is a better method than other reliability methods; the MCIS algorithm must also be considered to be most efficient. Also, these two sets of methods show a significant difference in the reliability index with the former set producing higher values. Also at a lower corrosion ratio the deviation is large, whereas as the corrosion ratio becomes very high ($d/t > 30\%$) all methods converge to similar values.

When comparing the two strength models, clearly the prediction of Chen et al. [21] model shows lower reliability than the prediction by RAM PIPE [12]. However, when corrosion ratio reaches 6% the reliability prediction by RAM PIPE [12] decreases drastically with almost a linear trend.

Fig. 5 Reliability index prediction by Chen et al. [21] (a) and by RAM PIPE [12] (b) strength model at different corrosion ratios

The operating pressure in the high strength pipelines must be higher than the conventional low-grade pipelines that may increase failure probability at a higher level of corrosion. The present study assumes the maximum operating pressure to be 72 % of design yield pressure. However, the operating pressure may be assigned to different values. Figure 6 (a) and Figure 6 (b) illustrates the trends of variation of reliability index with different operating pressure at different levels of corrosion. The trend can be acknowledged as a linear variation; also all curves are almost parallel indicating that reliability index is

equally sensitive at all corrosion ratios. Obviously higher operating pressure and increased corrosion lead to minimum reliability and vice versa. The information extracted from the results of Fig. 6 (a) and Fig. 6 (b) show that the reliability indices can reach zero values (very high failure probability) at certain points. Also, the information can be traced to define lower limits of operating pressure. A threshold reliability index of 3 may be used and most favorable operating pressure could be obtained at given corrosion ratio.

The role of appropriate strength model is also crucial in any reliability analysis as it is clear from the comparison in Fig. 6 (a) and (b). The model from Chen et al. predicts $\beta = 3$ at reliability around 57 MPa operating pressure for the corrosion ratio of 4, while the RAM PIPE model predicts the same safety level at 61 MPa.

As discussed earlier in this paper the thick high strength are different from other pipelines with respect to high σ_y/σ_t (yield to tensile strength) ratio and $\lambda = t/D$ (thickness to diameter) ratio [32][40]. The influence of changing these dimensionless parameters on reliability is further assessed and illustrated. As expected Chen et al model presents some significant variation in reliability with σ_y/σ_t ratio (see Fig. 7 (a) and (b)). Among a few other available models for high strength pipelines, the effect of σ_y/σ_t ratio has not been taken into account [32][41]. However, the reliability increment is small (1.3) with respect to increase in σ_y/σ_t ratio (0.7 to 0.95) in Chen et al. model, while there is no effect of σ_y/σ_t in RAM PIPE model. Another interesting observation drawn from Fig 7 (a) is that at each corrosion ratio the trend is similar and equidistant.

The distinction of a thick and thin pipeline is based on λ (t/D) or D/t ratio, the effect of being thick or thin pipelines on reliability are addressed in Fig. 8 (a) and (b). Initial λ is crucial for the reliability of pipelines, as very small λ results into very low reliability. Reliability increases with an increase in λ ; however at higher λ reliability curve tends to become horizontal. Chen et al model assumes high failure probability for no corrosion (0 levels) at λ little more than 0.02. Both models show significant deviation

in reliability trends which again shows the importance of appropriate burst strength model for reliability assessment.

Fig. 6 Variation in reliability index with operating pressure by Chen et al. [21] (a) and by RAM PIPE [12] (b) strength models at different corrosion levels

Fig. 7 Variation in reliability index with σ_y/σ_t ratio by Chen et al. [21] strength models at different corrosion levels

Fig. 8 Variation in reliability index with λ by Chen et al. [21] (a) and by RAM PIPE [12] (b) strength models at different corrosion ratios

Fig. 9. α – values (sensitivity factors) for limit state function of Chen et al. [21] (a) and RAM PIPE [12] (b) models at corrosion ratio $d/t=19\%$.

The relative importance of each variable on the limit state function and thus on reliability can be determined by sensitivity analysis. The sensitivity factors (α) are defined in section 5.1 and they can be expressed by Eq. 11. The sensitivity factors are calculated at increasing corrosion defects with the probabilistic model of the corresponding variables. The sensitivity factors of the limit state function defined based on the model proposed by Chen et al. [21] (Fig. 9a) and RAM PIPE [12] (Fig. 9b) are estimated for corrosion ratio 19%. It can be inferred that model uncertainty factor, depth of corrosion, operating pressure and material strengths are the most important variables. The comparison would imply

that the operating pressure is a significantly more important variable in Chen et al. [21] model than in RAM PIPE [12]. The diameter has almost no effect in both of the models, whereas thickness has low significance.

The effect of increasing corrosion defect on the sensitivity factors of the basic variable is clarified further. The sensitivity factors of different variables for Chen et al. and RAM PIPE [12] model respectively with different corrosion ratios are illustrated in Fig. 10 (a) and Fig. 10 (b). The underlying curves suggest that both models exhibit similar trends of variation in the basic variables. The highest variation is observed for depth of corrosion followed by model uncertainty factor in both of the models making them the most sensitive variables, respectively. Operating pressure attains constant value at all levels of corrosion, while material properties (yield and tensile strength in Chen et al. [21] model and tensile strength in RAM PIPE) have shown small decrement with increasing corrosion level. In both, the model diameter remains non important ($\alpha \cong 0$) throughout all the levels of corrosion while thickness influence is also negligible on limit state and remains at a constant near zero value.

Fig. 10. α – values (sensitivity factors) for limit state function of Chen et al. [21] (a) and RAM PIPE [12] (b) models for different corrosion ratios

Comparing Fig.10 (a) and Fig. 10 (b), it can be perceived how different models lead to distinct sensitivities. At a lower corrosion defect RAM PIPE model suggests higher importance of model uncertainty factor, Chen et al. model advocates comparatively higher importance of operating pressure. Until 33% of corrosion ratio in both models, the model uncertainty factor shows the highest influence on reliability. At a higher corrosion ratio (>33%) the influence of depth of corrosion dominates over the influence by all other variables. Both factors (d and P_o) observe similar values at each corrosion level by the two models.

6. Conclusions

This paper assesses the structural reliability of thick high strength pipelines with corrosion defects. It starts with a brief introduction of a new equation for burst pressure proposed by Chen et al. [21], which is validated by comparing with experimental data, DNV and B31G codes and RAM PIPE approach. Model uncertainty factors are derived from the comparison of experimental data from literature and the burst strength models' predictions for intact and corroded pipes. The limit state function is then defined in terms of operating pressure and calibrated burst strength of pipelines.

The stochastic models of basic geometry, loading, material properties random variables are defined with certain assumptions like the operating pressure is assumed to be 72% of burst pressure. The model uncertainty factor is also assumed as a random variable with properties like statistical moments and distributions identified. Limit state functions are formulated for intact pipelines using the strength models by Chen et al., DNV, B 31G and RAM PIPE and different reliability methods are used to assess the structural reliability of pipelines. The reliability indices estimated are compared by reliability methods like FORM, MCIS, FOSM and CMC. The influence of reliability methods on and strength models on reliability estimation is discussed. Later a sensitivity analysis demonstrates that the material strength, model uncertainty factors and operating pressure have the major importance for intact pipelines.

Additionally, an extensive reliability assessment is conducted on corroded pipelines using limit state functions defined by Chen et al. and RAM PIPE models for burst pressure. Probabilistic models are

defined for different corrosion defects depth and corresponding distribution parameters are estimated. The reliability indices and sensitivity factors are computed for increasing corrosion defect. Comparison of the results obtained using Chen and RAM PIPE strength model and reliability algorithms have been illustrated. The influence of variation in operating pressure on reliability is investigated. RAM PIPE model overestimates reliability index at lower corrosion while underestimates the reliability index at higher corrosion ratios. The results demonstrated that model uncertainty factor, depth of corrosion and operating pressure respectively are more important parameters in corroded pipelines. It has been emphasized that the accuracy of reliability assessment is also dependent on the burst strength model.

Finally, it can be stated that the model uncertainty factors have higher influence than other variables, however at a very high corrosion ratio, depth of corrosion dominates. Another conclusion drawn is at lower levels of corrosion the material properties have more influence than other variables.

The present study can be useful to assess the structural integrity of high strength pipelines and plan maintenance activities. It also proposes a framework for early reliability assessment for any equipment. Although, the reliability analysis for long corrosion defects with correlated depth and length of corrosion in high strength pipelines should be carried out separately.

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Appendix A. Comparison of the predictions by burst strength models with test data for intact pipelines
(source [20][33][34])

Exp. No.	D (mm)	t (mm)	σ_y (MPa)	σ_t (MPa)	Exp. (MPa)	Chen et al. (MPa)	DNV (MPa)	B31G (MPa)	RAM PIPE (MPa)
1	1117.6	14.1	622.0	716.0	21.7	19.9	19.2	17.3	20.1
2	762.0	9.5	579.0	761.0	20.0	19.5	20.2	15.9	21.1
3	1219.0	18.3	607.0	751.0	22.2	24.0	24.0	20.0	25.2
4	1219.0	18.3	644.0	776.0	23.0	25.2	24.8	21.3	26.0
5	914.0	13.0	761.0	878.0	25.8	27.5	26.6	23.8	27.9
6	1222.0	18.9	619.0	724.0	26.7	24.6	23.9	21.1	25.0
7	1067.0	18.9	599.0	704.0	24.6	27.4	26.7	23.3	27.9
8	914.0	20.0	679.0	715.0	31.3	36.2	33.6	32.7	35.2
9	457.0	9.8	645.0	709.0	36.8	34.5	32.6	30.4	34.2
10	390.8	12.8	807.0	869.0	59.6	66.0	61.8	58.2	64.7
11	247.0	9.9	641.2	717.0	61.4	65.7	62.6	56.3	65.6
12	179.4	8.9	468.8	737.7	77.9	70.0	81.3	51.4	85.1
13	252.2	13.5	606.7	703.3	81.2	86.0	83.4	71.4	87.4
14	162.2	9.8	602.0	776.0	86.6	102.0	104.8	80.0	109.8
15	179.7	10.4	618.4	723.9	92.4	95.3	93.0	78.4	97.4
16	67.3	3.9	689.5	834.3	113.1	109.0	108.2	88.2	113.3
17	179.7	10.3	848.0	917.0	118.6	124.9	117.5	107.3	123.1
18	89.7	6.5	696.4	751.5	119.3	129.9	122.4	110.2	128.2
19	179.6	12.0	779.1	896.3	133.8	139.3	135.0	114.7	141.4
20	179.5	13.3	834.3	903.2	152.4	160.9	151.9	136.1	159.1
21	198.2	14.7	908.0	992.8	171.7	175.6	166.4	147.7	174.4
22	198.2	14.6	908.0	992.8	173.7	174.9	165.8	147.2	173.7
23	180.1	14.9	908.0	992.8	178.6	197.5	187.5	164.8	196.5
24	89.0	14.4	606.7	730.8	294.4	289.7	296.5	216.1	310.6

Appendix B. Comparison of the predictions by Chen et al. [21] with test data and predictions by RAM PIPE for corroded pipelines. (source [36][37])

Exp. No.	D (mm)	t (mm)	σ_y (MPa)	σ_t (MPa)	d (mm)	Exp. (MPa)	Chen et al. (MPa)	RAM PIPE (MPa)
1	342	13.5	840	980	0.24	80.6	85.8	81.2
2	342	13.5	840	980	0.64	80.2	83.3	75.4
3	342	13.5	840	980	2.54	74.5	71.5	58.1

4	342	13.5	840	980	3.64	66.1	64.6	50.3
5	252	15.7	930	1070	0.33	143.0	151.5	139.2
6	252	15.7	930	1070	1.43	136.0	141.5	117.5
7	252	15.7	930	1070	2.63	130.0	130.4	101.3
8	252	15.7	930	1070	4.53	110.0	112.6	80.9
9	1219	19.9	585	715	15.41	7.6	5.7	4.5
10	1219	19.9	585	715	4.12	21.4	19.9	17.8
11	1219	19.9	592	723	7.44	17.7	16.0	13.5
12	1219	19.9	592	723	1.77	23.3	23.1	21.7
13	1219	13.8	568	705	10.78	4.7	3.7	3.1
14	1219	13.8	568	705	2.30	15.3	14.1	13.2
15	1219	13.8	589	731	5.45	12.0	10.7	9.4
16	1219	13.8	589	731	1.54	16.1	15.6	14.8
17	1320	22.9	782	803	2.52	27.0	28.9	24.7
18	1320	22.9	782	803	2.27	27.7	29.3	25.2
19	1320	22.9	782	803	2.31	27.5	29.2	25.1
20	1320	22.9	782	803	6.73	21.3	23.0	18.3
21	1320	22.9	782	803	6.73	21.8	23.0	18.3
22	1320	22.9	782	803	6.57	22.0	23.2	18.5
23	1320	22.9	782	803	11.45	15.9	16.4	12.3
24	1320	22.9	782	803	11.45	15.7	16.4	12.3
25	1320	22.9	782	803	11.45	15.9	16.4	12.3
26	1320	22.9	782	803	18.55	6.2	6.3	4.4
27	1320	22.9	782	803	19.01	5.5	5.6	4.0
28	1320	22.9	782	803	18.55	6.4	6.3	4.4
29	1320	20.6	782	803	2.06	23.2	26.3	22.7
30	1320	20.6	782	803	5.89	18.9	20.9	16.8
31	1320	20.6	782	803	11.33	13.2	13.2	10.0
32	1320	20.6	782	803	16.48	5.1	5.9	4.3
33	1320	22.9	782	803	4.58	25.0	26.0	21.4
34	1320	22.9	782	803	4.58	25.7	26.0	21.4
35	1320	22.9	782	803	11.45	16.0	16.4	12.3
36	1320	22.9	782	803	11.45	16.2	16.4	12.3
37	1320	22.9	782	803	18.32	6.3	6.6	4.7
38	1320	22.9	782	803	18.32	6.3	6.6	4.7
39	1320	20.6	782	803	4.12	21.8	23.4	19.4
40	1320	20.6	782	803	10.30	14.3	14.7	11.2
41	1320	20.6	782	803	16.85	5.1	5.4	3.9
42	1320	22.9	782	803	2.29	28.6	29.2	25.1
43	1320	22.9	782	803	2.29	28.2	29.2	25.1
44	1320	22.9	782	803	6.87	22.5	22.8	18.1

45	1320	22.9	782	803	6.87	22.1	22.8	18.1
46	1320	22.9	782	803	11.45	15.1	16.4	12.3
47	1320	22.9	782	803	11.45	15.5	16.4	12.3
48	1320	22.9	782	803	18.32	5.6	6.6	4.7
49	1320	22.9	782	803	18.32	5.7	6.6	4.7
50	1320	20.6	782	803	2.27	24.6	26.0	22.3
51	1320	20.6	782	803	6.39	19.4	20.2	16.2
52	1320	20.6	782	803	10.30	14.2	14.7	11.2
53	1320	20.6	782	803	15.86	5.1	6.8	4.9
54	1320	22.9	782	803	11.45	18.1	16.4	12.3
55	1320	22.9	782	803	11.45	15.4	16.4	12.3
56	1320	22.9	782	803	11.45	17.9	16.4	12.3
57	1320	22.9	782	803	11.45	15.0	16.4	12.3

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